

Energy $\rightarrow \hbar/\Delta t$ and Momentum $\rightarrow \hbar/\Delta x$ from $E = pc + m_0 c^2$?

Part 3

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In Part 1, we argued that special relativity introduces two sets of measures, $\Delta x = \hbar/p$, $\Delta t = \hbar/E$ (linked with 2-slit interference, i.e. stochastic interactions in space with fixed p) and Δx_1 , Δt_1 , linked with $\Delta x_1 = v \Delta t_1$, for $v = \text{constant}$.

In Part 2, we argued that Δx_1 , Δt_1 are linked with Newtonian mechanics which is deterministic $x_1(t_1)$, but also allows for a probabilistic view: $P(x) = dx/L$, where L is an arbitrary length (and a similar expression for $P(t)$). Δx and Δt were argued to be linked with periodic probabilities in space which had to ultimately be linked to $P(x)$, $P(t)$. This, we suggested, led to $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-iEt)$.

Here we ask: What happens in the case of a bound particle? In the Newtonian picture, $V(x)$ represents energy at x_1 in dx_1 . In this view, in dx_1 which may be arbitrarily small, there is a constant $v = dx_1/dt_1$ in dx_1 to first order. As a result, any interaction with $V(x)$ occurs in dx_1 . This contradicts the $\Delta x = \hbar/p$ picture which suggests that a fixed p , which represents kinetic energy $pp/2m$, cannot be fixed within dx_1 .

The question becomes: From a statistical point of view, how does one combine the Δx , Δt and Δx_1 , Δt_1 scenarios? If one cannot have a fixed p forced into a Δx_1 , which may become arbitrarily small, one may suggest a statistical average of p 's with weights $a(p) \exp(ipx)$ at dx_1 . Given that the p may be at different places in Δx , then the force rendering from $V(x)$ cannot also be at a point x_1 in dx_1 (except on average). Furthermore, force rendering changes momentum and so in the Δx picture, one considers this as the physical mechanics. Thus, Newtonian mechanics appears through the taking of averages. $V(x)$ itself may be considered an average $\text{Sum over } k \sum V_k \exp(ikx)$. In other words, Δx takes precedence and forces one to recognize space in terms of dx , but as noted in Part 2, one cannot simply ignore Newtonian mechanics.

Delta x, Delta p and Delta x1, Delta p1 Schemes and a Basic Contradiction

In Part I, we argued that two sets of variable schemes, Δx , Δt (associated with stochastic interactions of a constant p , divorced from time, and not fixed at a given x_1 exists in special relativity together with the usual Newtonian Δx_1 , Δt_1 , where $\Delta x_1 = v \Delta t_1$. There is already a contradiction at the level of a constant p and v , because the Δx_1 , Δt_1 scheme is deterministic and the former, stochastic. Thus, for Δx , Δt , there is a constant p and v and kinetic energy $= .5mv^2$, but one cannot fix the position.

In Part 2, we suggested that a way to reconcile the Newtonian and Δx , Δt stochastic picture is to try to write a $P(x) dx$ for a constant v in the Newtonian case. This is;

$$P(x)dx = dx/L \quad ((1)) \quad \text{where } L \text{ is an arbitrary length}$$

We argued that a uniform distribution associated with fixed:

$$\Delta x = \hbar/p \quad \text{and} \quad \Delta t = \hbar/E \quad ((2))$$

leads to a periodic probability in p_x and E_t which should be compatible with ((1)) and a similar expression for $P(t)$.

As a result, we argued that Δx , Δt has physical consequences for interactions and cited 2-slit interference and one dimensional reflection-refraction. This still begs the question: What happens in the case of a bound state?

Issue with a Bound State

The Δx , Δt scheme deals with a fixed p which is stochastically at different positions with a probability, $\exp(ipx)$. Time is not needed in time-independent scenarios because one does not have $\Delta x = v \Delta t$. One has $p^2/2m = \text{kinetic energy}$ and p , but no fixed position. As a result, an interaction leads to changes in p , but at different positions, as in a 2-slit situation.

This leads to a basic problem with the Newtonian picture of:

$$\text{Constant } v \text{ to first order in } dx_1 \text{ (arbitrarily small) with a force acting in } dx_1 \quad ((3))$$

In the Δx scheme, $\Delta x = \hbar/p$ and cannot be arbitrarily small and so a fixed p may appear at different positions linked with different $V(x)$ values. If one considers the Newtonian work equation, one may see that it is based on $\text{velocity} = \Delta x_1 / \Delta t_1$ and this no longer holds for the Δx , Δt scheme.

$$dp/dt = F \rightarrow dp \, dx/dt = F \, dx \quad \text{where } v = dx/dt = \Delta x_1 / \Delta t_1 \quad ((4))$$

It is ((4)), however, that is used in a Newtonian problem with $F = -dV/dx$. The question then becomes: How can one make ((4)) compatible with the Δx , Δt scheme?

The Δx , Δt scheme is stochastic and so the notion of velocity is problematic. We suggest the following:

Newtonian mechanics uses Δx_1 in a time-independent picture with $V(x_1)$ and a constant p , v at x_1 . Δx_1 can be made as small as possible.

Δx , on the other hand, is \hbar/p and is linked with a probability $\exp(ipx)$. One may suggest that one has an average of p values at a fixed x_1 in dx_1 , because no p is fixed to dx_1 . This average is based on $\exp(ipx)$ which shows the physical gradations \hbar/p . Thus:

$$\text{Average kinetic energy at } x_1 = \frac{1}{2m} \frac{\sum_i p^2 a(p) \exp(ipx)}{\{\sum_i a(p) \exp(ipx)\}} \quad ((5)) \quad (\text{one dimension})$$

The Δx scheme can only be restricted to the Newtonian dx_1 (arbitrarily small length) via a statistical average. In such a case, one may still have $V(x_1)$ at x_1 in dx_1 , but how do impulse hits occur?

In previous notes, we argued that one may write:

$$\sum_k V_k \exp(ikx) = V(x) \quad ((6))$$

and consider momentum transfers in a stochastic scheme of $\exp(ipx)\exp(ikx) = \exp(i(p+k)x)$ ((7))

As a result, one has various momentum values which are linked with \hbar/p intervals and stochastic hits and can only have the notion of an average kinetic energy at a given x_1 in dx_1 and hence a v_{rms} at x_1 .

Newtonian Limit

Based on the above arguments, it seems that to recover Newtonian mechanics from the above scheme, one has to actually remove the average over p at x_1 with a fixed p . This is similar to the case of asking: What is the Newtonian limit of a free particle? The free particle is represented by $\exp(ipx)/\sqrt{L}$ for any p and $\exp(-ipx)\exp(ipx)/L = 1/L = P(x)$. There is no Newtonian limit here. One simply uses $P(x)=1/L$ if one wishes to have Newtonian mechanics.

Similarities with an Ideal Gas

We have argued in previous notes that the quantum bound state has similarities with an ideal gas except for the fact that in the gas, stochasticity arises from interactions, whereas it is built-in for a single quantum particle, i.e. $\Delta x = \hbar/p$, $\Delta t = \hbar/E$, without and stochastic interaction scheme (based on temperature T) appearing a priori.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we try to argue that special relativity yields two schemes, the usual $\Delta x_1 = v \Delta t_1$ (constant v) Newtonian mechanics picture and a Δx , Δt stochastic scheme linked with p , $pp/2m$ appearing/interacting at different points with $\Delta x = \hbar/p$. We try to combine the two schemes for a bound state picture, but stress that one cannot erase the stochastic p over $\hbar/p = dx$ length. This means that it makes no sense to have a single v within dx_1 and this implies a statistical average. Furthermore, Newtonian mechanics associated a v with work $F dx$ and so this too becomes an average concept or a rms one. Thus, $V(x)$ (potential) from Newtonian mechanics represents an average as well in this scheme. As a result, one may write: $1/2m \{ \sum_i p_i^2 \exp(ipx) a(p) \} / \{ \sum_i a(p) \exp(ipx) \} + V(x) = E$ and now x becomes the x_1 of the Newtonian scheme, but $\exp(ipx)$ enforces the $\Delta x = \hbar/p$ gradations of the Δx , Δp scheme.